

ASPECTS OF THE FOOD AND FEEDING HABITS OF AFRICAN SNAKEHEAD *Parachanna obscura* (Gunther, 1861) IN ORASHI RIVER, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The food and feeding habits of African snakehead *Parachanna obscura* from the fresh water reaches of Orashi River, Rivers State, Nigeria were investigated. A total of Eighty (80) adults and juveniles fish samples were collected from the local fishers. Fishes were caught using hook and line and non-returned traditional basket traps. The stomachs were open for each fish and the contents was removed and preserved in 4% formalin. Analysis of stomach contents was done by a combination of frequency of occurrence and numerical methods. The food items in the stomach of *P. obscura* covered a wide feeding range, juveniles fishes were basically benthic feeding on nematode worms, fish larvae, tadpole larvae and insect. Adult *P. obscura* are surface or benthic feeders, feeding mostly on fish, nematode worms, crustaceans, insect and tadpoles. This suggests that *P. obscura* is a carnivore and is also considered as piscivore-insectivore-invertivore in feeding habits.

Key words:Orashi River,*Parachanna obscura*, Stomach content

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INTRODUCTION

Members of the family Channidae are freshwater fishes occurring in Africa and Asia. Snake heads are composed of only two genera, *channa* which includes all Asian species, and *parachanna*, which include all African species. The two genera differ mainly in the morphology of the air breathing suprabranchial pharyngeal cavities that permit direct breathing of atmospheric air, allowing the fish to survive for long periods outside the water, while the latter being less developed (Teugelset *et al.*, 1984).It is commonly found in the vegetative swamps usually in great abundance shortly after the raining season when the river banks decreased. *Parachanna obscura* is likely among the most beautiful of the African species and because of this, it is a popular fish in display aquaria. *P. obscura* is also an economic species. In all the markets of Mbiama in rivers state, it is sold fresh and alive but at a high cost.

The specie, is a general carnivorous feeder as regards both size range and diversity of organism that are consumed by fish, thus they are obligate piscivores. Ecologically, the species is an insectivore-Piscivore-invertivore in feeding habits. *Parachanna obscura* are strictly carnivorous fishes feeding on earthworms, tadpoles, shrimps, smaller fishes and other aquatic animals (Chen, 1976). Reed *et al.*, (1967) and Bardachet *et al.*, (1972) all confirmed the feeding habits of the fish to be extremely voracious and predatory or carnivorous and having a piscivorous predation especially in the adult stage, therefore care should be taken in the selection of other fish to stock with them during polyculture. Victor and Akpocha, (1992) also stated that in monoculture system in Nigeria ponds, small size specimens of *P. obscura* (10 to 16cm SL) fed primarily on detritus and larval insects, whereas large size (16-24cm SL) consumed fish parts and juvenile with insects and fish making up the bulk of the diet.

The species have an elongated cylindrical body; flattened head, long, entirely soft rayed dorsal and anal fins, a large mouth with well-developed teeth on both upper and lower jaws, tube-like anterior nostrils; a round to

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somewhat truncate caudal fin; cycloid body scales; shield-like scales on a head that superficially resemble that of a snake; a lengthy, elongated swim bladder reaching to the caudal peduncle region; and an accessory air breathing apparatus (supra branchial organ) in the head region (Teugels, 1985).

Despite its numerical abundance and protein value, there is a paucity of information on a detailed study of its food and feeding habits in the vegetative swamps of Orashi River, Rivers State. In all groups of air breathing fishes, snakeheads constitute distinct units of food fishes, generating high market value and demand because of their taste, few intramuscular spines and medicinal value. They are of great interest to conservationist due to their primitiveness (Kees *et al.*, 2002). Several works has been done by various workers on the food and feeding habits of many fish species in various water bodies. This study was carried out to investigate the food and feeding habit of the African snakehead, *Parachanna obscura* in Orashi River, Rivers State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study area

The Orashi River is located between latitudes $4^{\circ} 76$ and $4^{\circ} 45N$ and longitude $6^{\circ} 75$ and $6^{\circ} 45E$ in the Niger Delta area of Nigeria. The river is a distributary of the River Niger which arises from northern boundary of Rivers State with Imo State. It is one of the series of the Niger Delta rivers which drain into the Atlantic Ocean and is connected to other rivers via creeks in the coastal area of the Niger Delta (Ezekiel, 1986). The river is narrow and steep as it flows southwards, it widens and the steep sidedness gradually disappears starting from the middle reaches. The system is lotic throughout the year; the lotic period reaches its peak in January to February (dry season) when the water level has fallen to the maximum. In August - September (wet season), the lotic nature of the river is reduced due to flooding (Ezekiel, 1986). Climate condition is tropical the area lies within the rain forest belt. The annual rainfall is about 3,800mm. Vegetation is made up of submerged macrophytes such as *Nymphaea lotus*, *Lemna erecta*, *Utricularia species*, *Cyclosorus species*, *Commelia species* and *Hyponea species*. The riparian vegetation is composed of tree canopy which is made up of *Costusafer*, *Raphiahokeri*, *Nitrogena species*, *Bambosa vulgaris*. The river system provides nursery and breeding grounds for a large variety of fish species. Numerous human activities such as fishing, sand mining, dredging, logging of timber and transportation takes place.

Fish samples were collected between January and December 2010, using hook and line and non-returned traditional basket traps. Specimens were examined for food immediately after capture and were transported in an ice-chest to the laboratory. Fish specimen collected was given a registration number which indicates date of capture, sex, weight and length. The body lengths (total length and standard length) were measured on a measuring board graduated in centimeter, while fish body weights were taken to the nearest gram (gm) on a top loading balance. The guts were removed from dissected specimens and split open and the content of each stomach was analyzed immediately or stored in 5% formalin. The stomach contents were analyzed using the frequency of occurrence and numerical methods (Bagenal, 1978). In the frequency of occurrence each food item was used to indicate the proportion of fishes eating a particular food item. The merits and limitations of these methods have been discussed by (Dunn, 1954; Crips, 1963, Fagade and Olaniyan, 1972). In numerical methods, the number of individual in each category is recorded for all stomachs and the total is expressed as a proportion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Food composition

Tables 1 and 2 shows the list of food items found in the stomach of *P. obscura*. The relative contributions of the food items are expressed by frequency of occurrence and numerical methods. A total of 80 stomachs were examined. Seven major items constituted the diet of *P. obscura*, three forming the dominant stomach content.

Food composition for juvenile's *P. obscura*:

In the numerical analysis nematodes were dominant and composed of 22.5% of the items in the stomach, fish larva made up 16.3% while tadpole larva made up 15%, insect parts 10%, daphnia and cyclops 11.3 and 8.8% respectively. Vegetables were least with 2.5% and 13.8% made up empty stomach.

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Food items were contained in sixty-four stomachs and nematodes were present in 33.8%, fish larva were contained in 18.8% of the stomach, tadpole larva 7.5%, insect parts 6.3%, daphnia and Cyclops were contained in 5.0 and 3.8% respectively. Vegetables were least occurred in 2.5% and 22.5% made up empty stomach for frequency of occurrence.

Food composition for adult *P. obscura*:

Adult *P. obscura* feed mostly on fish than other food items, and then followed by crustaceans and few nematodes while juveniles' *P. obscura* also fed mostly on nematodes, fish larvae and tadpole larvae. The stomachs of both juvenile and adult *P. obscura* do not contain any algae as observed throughout the period of my investigation.

Nematodes were dominant and composed of 27.5% of the items in the stomach, fish larva made up 25%, daphnia 21.3%, insect's parts (10.0%), tadpole larva and Cyclops was 6.3% each. The least of 3.8% was obtained for vegetables, no empty stomach was observed.

Food items were contained in sixty-four stomachs and nematodes were present in 30.0%, fish larva were contained in 17.5%, insect parts were contained in 12.5%, tadpole larva 8.8%, Cyclops 3.8% and the least of 2.5% was contained in vegetables for frequency of occurrence.

Table 1: Analysis of Stomach Contents of Juveniles *P. obscura* by frequency of occurrence and numerical methods

Food Items	Numerical	%	Frequency	%
Nematodes	18	22.5	27	33.8
Fish larvae	13	16.3	13	18.8
Tadpole larvae	12	15.0	6	7.5
Insects parts	8	10.0	5	6.3
Daphnia	9	11.3	4	5.0
Cyclops	7	8.8	3	3.8
Vegetables	2	2.5	2	2.5
Empty stomach	11	13.8	16	22.5
Total		100.2		100.2

Table 2: Analysis of Stomach Contents of Adult *P. obscura* by frequency of occurrence and numerical methods

Food Items	Numerical	%	Frequency	%
Nematodes	22	27.5	24	30.0
Fish larvae	20	25.0	14	17.5
Tadpole larvae	5	6.3	7	8.8
Insects parts	8	10.0	10	12.5
Daphnia	17	21.3	4	5.0
Cyclops	5	6.3	3	3.8
Vegetables	3	3.8	2	2.5
Empty stomach	0	0	16	20.0
Total		100.2		100.1

Parachanna obscura has a wide feeding range; food composition shows a marked seasonal variation. The food range becomes drastically limited in the dry season when the occurrence shows insect parts, and nematodes as predominant in the stomach contents of *P. obscura*.

Insect parts were found in the diet of *P. obscura*. The insects might have been swallowed by the fish while feeding on the surface merging or level of the water. Parts of insects like pieces of exoskeleton, wings legs (fragments) etc. were also common. In the absence of fish which is the basic food item, insects acting as secondary food item of *P. obscura*. Throughout the period of observation, crustaceans were observed in their stomach.

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The food items in the stomach of *Parachanna obscura*, suggest that they are euryphagous (i.e. feeding on a wide range of organisms). The fairly uniform, rate of feeding also attributed partly to the irregularly continuous nature of feeding of the fish which permit the year round utilization of the fish as a bio control agent of young Tilapia (Cruz and Laudénica, 1980) in a polyculture. After a through survey of the stomach contents, it becomes clear and necessary to classify the species as: those feeding on other macroscopic animals (predatory species) mainly the adults. The three main categories of food and the basis of their importance in the diets of fish include the followings: basic food, which is normally eaten by fish which comprises most of the stomach content. Secondary food, that is frequently found in the stomach content but in a smaller amounts and incidental food, that which is found only rarely in the stomach contents. The food composition also shows a marked seasonal variation. The food range becomes drastically limited in the dry season when the occurrence shows insect parts, and nematodes as predominant in the stomach contents of *P. obscura*. It has been demonstrated and emphasized in the result that as *P. obscura* increases in size and length; it changes its food completely, becoming more Ichthyophagous with age. The juveniles feeds mainly on nematodes, fish larvae, tadpoles larvae and insects parts, while adults specimen or species predominately fed on fish, such as Tilapia species, few nematode worms, tadpoles, insects, and crustaceans. Consequently, there is no obvious interspecific as regards the food intake between these size groups since the size of the preys taken in each group differs. This change in diet with growth not only offers a wider range of food resources to the species but also reduces possible competition between the adults and juveniles to some extent. From observations, it was notice that the fish also exhibits an over lapping in the food and feeding habits in order to avoid inter and intra –specific competition for available food. This is an important strategy for survival and an advantage over the fish species competing for a specific food items. This explains the availability of *P. obscura* all year round (Fagade and Olaniyan, 1972). The monthly/ seasonal variations in feeding habit showed an increase in the stomach during the rainy season and decrease in the dry season. This may reflect a steady dwindling of food resources in a habit that is continually decreasing in volume with the onset of the dry season. Some of the variability in the diet composition of *P. obscura* may be explained on the basis of the change in water level. During the rainy season, there is a wide variety and abundance of food available due to high nutrient composition of the runoff from land which promotes plant growth and increases invertebrate (Moss, 1980). As the dry season approaches, the river become shallow and the abundance and variety of food decrease. Then *P. obscura* change its diet composition to insects or insect parts and nematodes. The seasonal change in temperature as a result of harmattan winds from the Sahara desert may also play an important role in reducing food availability and diversity.

P. obscura feeds on zooplankton like crustaceans which are represented by cladocerans (*Daphnia sp*) and copepods (cyclop) indicating the food preference of *P. obscura* for Zooplankton, insects parts or insects which constitutes their major diet during dry season. The various switches from one particular feeding habit to another from stage to stage as observed in this study, have been confirmed by various workers on yellow perch *Perca flavescens* from zooplankton to benthic prey (Wu and Culver, 1992), and from zooplankton to benthic invertebrate by snakehead (Qin and Fast, 1997), due to increase in gill raker size as the fish grew. The ability of *P. obscura* to feed at a number of different trophic levels coupled with potential for fast growth makes this species a promising candidate for commercial culture. As the species is widely used as human food throughout the area in which it occurs, it could easily be incorporated into locally operated polyculture systems with minimal inputs of expensive animal protein in the feed (Hyslop, 1986). In comparison with other predatory fishes, this result confirmed to the study on the food and feeding habits of African pike (*Hepsetus odoe*) in Ado-Ekiti reservoir (Idowu and Ugwumba, 2006). It was observed that fish was the most important food of *Hepsetus odoe* in the reservoir constituting about 85% while insects ranked next with 15%. Other food items such as prawn and gastropods has less than 1% R1 value each.

CONCLUSION

Specimens with empty stomachs appeared among juveniles in higher proportion than in adults. In order to see whether there is any seasonal variation in the feeding intensity, a monthly analysis of the data was made. *P. obscura* juveniles fed 33.8% on nematodes and have 22.5% empty stomach while the incidence of empty stomach was lesser in adults than in juveniles and the index of relative importance in adults shows that they feed mostly on fish and few nematodes than other food items has empty stomachs of about 20.0%.

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